

Table S1. Summary Table of All Variables

Variable Label	Variable	Category	Total
Exploratory Variables			
Arab	ethnic__1	Yes	3 (0.1)
		No	3347 (99.9)
		(Missing)	0 (0.0)
Black	ethnic__2	Yes	1 (0.0)
		No	3349 (100.0)
		(Missing)	0 (0.0)
East Asian	ethnic__3	Yes	3292 (98.3)
		No	58 (1.7)
		(Missing)	0 (0.0)
South Asian	ethnic__4	Yes	39 (1.2)
		No	3311 (98.8)
		(Missing)	0 (0.0)
West Asian	ethnic__5	Yes	1 (0.0)
		No	3349 (100.0)
		(Missing)	0 (0.0)
White	ethnic__7	Yes	9 (0.3)
		No	3341 (99.7)
		(Missing)	0 (0.0)
Aboriginal/First Nations	ethnic__8	Yes	1 (0.0)
		No	3349 (100.0)
		(Missing)	0 (0.0)
Healthcare Worker	healthwork_er term	Yes	271 (8.1)
		No	2996 (89.4)
		(Missing)	83 (2.5)
Microbio Lab Worker	labwork_er term	Yes	12 (0.4)
		No	3249 (97.0)
		(Missing)	89 (2.7)
Male	sex	Yes	1695 (50.6)
		No	1655 (49.4)
		(Missing)	0 (0.0)
Age (years)	age_estimate years	Median (IQR)	57.0 (38.0 to 71.0)
Pregnant	pregyn_rptestcd	Yes	49 (1.5)
		No	599 (17.9)
		(Missing)	2702 (80.7)
Chronic Cardiac Disease	chroniccard_m hyn	Yes	189 (5.6)

		No	3159 (94.3)
		(Missing)	2 (0.1)
Hypertension	hypertension_ mhyn	Yes	1746 (52.1)
		No	1601 (47.8)
		(Missing)	3 (0.1)
Chronic Pulmonary Disease	chronicpul_ mhyn	Yes	58 (1.7)
		No	3289 (98.2)
		(Missing)	3 (0.1)
Asthma	asthma_mhyn	Yes	249 (7.4)
		No	3099 (92.5)
		(Missing)	2 (0.1)
Chronic Kidney Disease	renal_mhyn	Yes	314 (9.4)
		No	3033 (90.5)
		(Missing)	3 (0.1)
Obesity	obesity_mhyn	Yes	520 (15.5)
		No	2689 (80.3)
		(Missing)	141 (4.2)
Moderate to Severe Liver Disease	modliver_ mhyn	Yes	8 (0.2)
		No	3340 (99.7)
		(Missing)	2 (0.1)
Mild Liver Disease	mildliv_ mhyn	Yes	15 (0.4)
		No	3333 (99.5)
		(Missing)	2 (0.1)
Asplenia	asplenia_mhyn	Yes	1 (0.0)
		No	3347 (99.9)
		(Missing)	2 (0.1)
Chronic Neurological Disorder	chronicneu_ mhyn	Yes	67 (2.0)
		No	3280 (97.9)
		(Missing)	3 (0.1)
Malignant Neoplasm	malignantneo_ mhyn	Yes	22 (0.7)
		No	3325 (99.3)
		(Missing)	3 (0.1)
Chronic Hematological Disease	chronhaemo_ mhyn	Yes	7 (0.2)
		No	3338 (99.6)
		(Missing)	5 (0.1)
AIDS/HIV	aidshiv_mhyn_ 2	Yes - on ART	16 (0.5)

		Yes - Not on ART	10 (0.3)
		No	443 (13.2)
		(Missing)	2881 (86.0)
Diabetes Mellitus	diabetes_mhy_n_2	Yes - Type 1	30 (0.9)
		Yes - Type 2	939 (28.0)
		Yes - Gestational	24 (0.7)
		No	2312 (69.0)
		(Missing)	45 (1.3)
Rheumatologic Disorder	rheumatology_mhyr	Yes	39 (1.2)
		No	3308 (98.7)
		(Missing)	3 (0.1)
Dementia	dementia_mhy_n	Yes	69 (2.1)
		No	3278 (97.9)
		(Missing)	3 (0.1)
Tuberculosis	tb_mhyn	Yes	30 (0.9)
		No	3318 (99.0)
		(Missing)	2 (0.1)
Malnutrition	malnutrition_mhyn	Yes	6 (0.2)
		No	3339 (99.7)
		(Missing)	5 (0.1)
Ever Smoker	smoking_mhyn	Yes	666 (19.9)
		No	2484 (74.1)
		(Missing)	200 (6.0)
COVID-19 Vaccine Count	vacc_cov19	Median (IQR)	2.0 (0.0 to 3.0)
Remdesivir	antiviral_cmtrt__7	Yes	1776 (53.0)
		No	1574 (47.0)
		(Missing)	0 (0.0)
Target Variables			
Mortality	mortality	Deceased	3220 (96.1)
		Discharged Alive	130 (3.9)
		(Missing)	0 (0.0)
Length of Hospital Stay (LoHS)	lohs	Median (IQR)	6.0(4.0 to 9.0)

Table S2. Exploratory Variables Stratified by Mortality Status

Variable	Category	Discharged Alive	Deceased	Fisher p-value	Chisq p-value
ethnic__1	Yes	3 (0.1)	0 (0.0)	1.000	1.000
	No	3217 (99.9)	130 (100.0)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)		
ethnic__2	Yes	1 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1.000	1.000
	No	3219 (100.0)	130 (100.0)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)		
ethnic__3	Yes	3164 (98.3)	128 (98.5)	1.000	1.000
	No	56 (1.7)	2 (1.5)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)		
ethnic__4	Yes	37 (1.1)	2 (1.5)	0.663	1.000
	No	3183 (98.9)	128 (98.5)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)		
ethnic__5	Yes	1 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1.000	1.000
	No	3219 (100.0)	130 (100.0)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)		
ethnic__7	Yes	9 (0.3)	0 (0.0)	1.000	1.000
	No	3211 (99.7)	130 (100.0)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)		
ethnic__8	Yes	1 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1.000	1.000
	No	3219 (100.0)	130 (100.0)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)		
healthwork_erterm	Yes	271 (8.4)	0 (0.0)	<0.001	0.001
	No	2869 (89.1)	127 (97.7)		
	(Missing)	80 (2.5)	3 (2.3)		
labwork_erterm	Yes	12 (0.4)	0 (0.0)	1.000	1.000
	No	3122 (97.0)	127 (97.7)		
	(Missing)	86 (2.7)	3 (2.3)		
sex	Yes	1626 (50.5)	69 (53.1)	0.592	0.626
	No	1594 (49.5)	61 (46.9)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)		
age_estimate years	Median (IQR)	56.0 (38.0 to 71.0)	73.0 (60.2 to 83.8)	<0.001 Mann Whitney	<0.001 Mann Whitney
pregyn_rptest cd	Yes	49 (1.5)	0 (0.0)	1.000	0.966
	No	592 (18.4)	7 (5.4)		
	(Missing)	2579 (80.1)	123 (94.6)		
chroniccard_mhyn	Yes	169 (5.2)	20 (15.4)	<0.001	<0.001
	No	3051 (94.8)	108 (83.1)		

	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	2 (1.5)		
hypertension_mhyn	Yes	1651 (51.3)	95 (73.1)	<0.001	<0.001
	No	1568 (48.7)	33 (25.4)		
	(Missing)	1 (0.0)	2 (1.5)		
chronicpul_mhyn	Yes	53 (1.6)	5 (3.8)	0.069	0.115
	No	3166 (98.3)	123 (94.6)		
	(Missing)	1 (0.0)	2 (1.5)		
asthma_mhyn	Yes	238 (7.4)	11 (8.5)	0.605	0.736
	No	2982 (92.6)	117 (90.0)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	2 (1.5)		
renal_mhyn	Yes	290 (9.0)	24 (18.5)	0.001	<0.001
	No	2930 (91.0)	103 (79.2)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	3 (2.3)		
obesity_mhyn	Yes	509 (15.8)	11 (8.5)	0.086	0.096
	No	2590 (80.4)	99 (76.2)		
	(Missing)	121 (3.8)	20 (15.4)		
modliver_mhyn	Yes	8 (0.2)	0 (0.0)	1.000	1.000
	No	3212 (99.8)	128 (98.5)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	2 (1.5)		
mildliv_mhyn	Yes	14 (0.4)	1 (0.8)	0.443	1.000
	No	3206 (99.6)	127 (97.7)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	2 (1.5)		
asplenia_mhyn	Yes	1 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1.000	1.000
	No	3219 (100.0)	128 (98.5)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	2 (1.5)		
chronicneu_mhyn	Yes	59 (1.8)	8 (6.2)	0.004	0.001
	No	3160 (98.1)	120 (92.3)		
	(Missing)	1 (0.0)	2 (1.5)		
malignantneo_mhyn	Yes	20 (0.6)	2 (1.5)	0.205	0.463
	No	3199 (99.3)	126 (96.9)		
	(Missing)	1 (0.0)	2 (1.5)		
chronhaemo_mhyn	Yes	7 (0.2)	0 (0.0)	1.000	1.000
	No	3211 (99.7)	127 (97.7)		
	(Missing)	2 (0.1)	3 (2.3)		
aidshiv_mhyn_2	Yes - on ART	16 (0.5)	0 (0.0)	1	0.461

	Yes - Not on ART	10 (0.3)	0 (0.0)		
	No	418 (13.0)	25 (19.2)		
	(Missing)	2776 (86.2)	105 (80.8)		
diabetes_mhy_n_2	Yes - Type 1	30 (0.9)	0 (0.0)	0.091	0.053
	Yes - Type 2	891 (27.7)	48 (36.9)		
	Yes - Gestational	24 (0.7)	24 (0.7)		
	No	2234 (69.4)	78 (60.0)		
	(Missing)	41 (1.3)	4 (3.1)		
rheumatology_mhyr	Yes	38 (1.2)	1 (0.8)	1.000	1.000
	No	3181 (98.8)	127 (97.7)		
	(Missing)	1 (0.0)	2 (1.5)		
dementia_mhyn	Yes	59 (1.8)	10 (7.7)	<0.001	<0.001
	No	3160 (98.1)	118 (90.8)		
	(Missing)	1 (0.0)	2 (1.5)		
tb_mhyn	Yes	27 (0.8)	3 (2.3)	0.105	0.196
	No	3193 (99.2)	125 (96.2)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	2 (1.5)		
malnutrition_mhyn	Yes	4 (0.1)	2 (1.5)	0.019	0.007
	No	3214 (99.8)	125 (96.2)		
	(Missing)	2 (0.1)	3 (2.3)		
smoking_mhyn	Yes	636 (19.8)	30 (23.1)	0.091	0.098
	No	2407 (74.8)	77 (59.2)		
	(Missing)	177 (5.5)	23 (17.7)		
vacc_cov19	Median (IQR)	2.0 (0.0 to 3.0)	0.0 (0.0 to 2.0)	<0.001 Mann Whitney	<0.001 Mann Whitney
antiviral_cmtr_t_7	Yes	1710 (53.1)	66 (50.8)	0.654	0.665
	No	1510 (46.9)	64 (49.2)		
	(Missing)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)		

Table S3. Performance Metrics of All Classification Models

Model	Resampling	Feature Selection	F-measure	AUPRC
Logistic Regression	No Resampling	No FS	0.97475	0.98455
Logistic Regression	No Resampling	ROC FS	0.97475	0.98116
Logistic Regression	No Resampling	Boruta	0.97475	0.98343
Logistic Regression	Over-Sampling	No FS	0.81536	0.98369

Logistic Regression	Over-Sampling	ROC FS	0.79518	0.98070
Logistic Regression	Over-Sampling	Boruta	0.81536	0.98284
Logistic Regression	SMOTE	No FS	0.81210	0.98364
Logistic Regression	SMOTE	ROC FS	0.79031	0.98177
Logistic Regression	SMOTE	Boruta	0.81569	0.98282
Logistic Regression	ADASYN	No FS	0.81244	0.98330
Logistic Regression	ADASYN	ROC FS	0.78692	0.98153
Logistic Regression	ADASYN	Boruta	0.79815	0.98267
Logistic Regression	Under-Sampling	No FS	0.75743	0.97687
Logistic Regression	Under-Sampling	ROC FS	0.79143	0.98087
Logistic Regression	Under-Sampling	Boruta	0.80808	0.98079
Logistic Regression	NearMiss	No FS	0.80992	0.98183
Logistic Regression	NearMiss	ROC FS	0.77830	0.97054
Logistic Regression	NearMiss	Boruta	0.76806	0.97994
Decision Tree	No Resampling	No FS	0.97475	0.97537
Decision Tree	No Resampling	ROC FS	0.97475	0.97537
Decision Tree	No Resampling	Boruta	0.97475	0.97537
Decision Tree	Over-Sampling	No FS	0.84650	0.98078
Decision Tree	Over-Sampling	ROC FS	0.77578	0.98015
Decision Tree	Over-Sampling	Boruta	0.84622	0.98064
Decision Tree	SMOTE	No FS	0.89003	0.97684
Decision Tree	SMOTE	ROC FS	0.79480	0.96726
Decision Tree	SMOTE	Boruta	0.87780	0.98092
Decision Tree	ADASYN	No FS	0.88813	0.97765
Decision Tree	ADASYN	ROC FS	0.78805	0.96718
Decision Tree	ADASYN	Boruta	0.86614	0.98316
Decision Tree	Under-Sampling	No FS	0.83617	0.96669
Decision Tree	Under-Sampling	ROC FS	0.71244	0.96098
Decision Tree	Under-Sampling	Boruta	0.77516	0.97698
Decision Tree	NearMiss	No FS	0.66391	0.98091
Decision Tree	NearMiss	ROC FS	0.77903	0.97758
Decision Tree	NearMiss	Boruta	0.77736	0.97816
Random Forest	No Resampling	No FS	0.97475	0.98501
Random Forest	No Resampling	ROC FS	0.97475	0.97954
Random Forest	No Resampling	Boruta	0.97475	0.98420
Random Forest	Over-Sampling	No FS	0.92659	0.98463
Random Forest	Over-Sampling	ROC FS	0.90713	0.97658
Random Forest	Over-Sampling	Boruta	0.91523	0.98291

Random Forest	SMOTE	No FS	0.95501	0.98607
Random Forest	SMOTE	ROC FS	0.92270	0.97473
Random Forest	SMOTE	Boruta	0.94560	0.98381
Random Forest	ADASYN	No FS	0.95170	0.98615
Random Forest	ADASYN	ROC FS	0.91728	0.97400
Random Forest	ADASYN	Boruta	0.93106	0.98266
Random Forest	Under-Sampling	No FS	0.79143	0.98427
Random Forest	Under-Sampling	ROC FS	0.77316	0.98160
Random Forest	Under-Sampling	Boruta	0.78457	0.98022
Random Forest	NearMiss	No FS	0.80776	0.98489
Random Forest	NearMiss	ROC FS	0.73084	0.97641
Random Forest	NearMiss	Boruta	0.78498	0.98555
Extreme Gradient Boosting	No Resampling	No FS	0.97550	0.98298
Extreme Gradient Boosting	No Resampling	ROC FS	0.97475	0.97611
Extreme Gradient Boosting	No Resampling	Boruta	0.97471	0.98040
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Over-Sampling	No FS	0.89840	0.98483
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Over-Sampling	ROC FS	0.84378	0.97874
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Over-Sampling	Boruta	0.85889	0.98249
Extreme Gradient Boosting	SMOTE	No FS	0.94297	0.98376
Extreme Gradient Boosting	SMOTE	ROC FS	0.89983	0.97579
Extreme Gradient Boosting	SMOTE	Boruta	0.91419	0.98513
Extreme Gradient Boosting	ADASYN	No FS	0.94400	0.98227
Extreme Gradient Boosting	ADASYN	ROC FS	0.90759	0.97606
Extreme Gradient Boosting	ADASYN	Boruta	0.90274	0.98377
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Under-Sampling	No FS	0.80952	0.97938
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Under-Sampling	ROC FS	0.77851	0.97958
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Under-Sampling	Boruta	0.77054	0.97767
Extreme Gradient Boosting	NearMiss	No FS	0.77303	0.98232
Extreme Gradient Boosting	NearMiss	ROC FS	0.72549	0.97403
Extreme Gradient Boosting	NearMiss	Boruta	0.79065	0.98365
K-Nearest Neighbors	No Resampling	No FS	0.95618	0.97673
K-Nearest Neighbors	No Resampling	ROC FS	0.97156	0.97417
K-Nearest Neighbors	No Resampling	Boruta	0.97318	0.97866
K-Nearest Neighbors	Over-Sampling	No FS	0.95863	0.97640
K-Nearest Neighbors	Over-Sampling	ROC FS	0.95625	0.97452
K-Nearest Neighbors	Over-Sampling	Boruta	0.95761	0.97887
K-Nearest Neighbors	SMOTE	No FS	0.95208	0.97915
K-Nearest Neighbors	SMOTE	ROC FS	0.94033	0.97187

K-Nearest Neighbors	SMOTE	Boruta	0.93930	0.97855
K-Nearest Neighbors	ADASYN	No FS	0.95043	0.97890
K-Nearest Neighbors	ADASYN	ROC FS	0.94043	0.97097
K-Nearest Neighbors	ADASYN	Boruta	0.94511	0.97783
K-Nearest Neighbors	Under-Sampling	No FS	0.74023	0.98223
K-Nearest Neighbors	Under-Sampling	ROC FS	0.78578	0.97868
K-Nearest Neighbors	Under-Sampling	Boruta	0.76072	0.97583
K-Nearest Neighbors	NearMiss	No FS	0.78472	0.97740
K-Nearest Neighbors	NearMiss	ROC FS	0.73858	0.97496
K-Nearest Neighbors	NearMiss	Boruta	0.76499	0.98058

- Note: Best model per algorithm based on initial evaluation is in **bold text and highlighted in blue**.

Table S4. Performance Metrics of All Regression Models

Model	Transformation	Feature Selection	MAE	RSQ
Linear Regression	No Transformation	No FS	6.38698	0.00026
Linear Regression	No Transformation	CAR Score	6.37056	0.00041
Linear Regression	No Transformation	Boruta	6.42769	0.00011
Linear Regression	Square Root	No FS	0.70966	0.02507
Linear Regression	Square Root	CAR Score	0.71209	0.02297
Linear Regression	Square Root	Boruta	0.71609	0.02120
Linear Regression	Yeo-Johnson	No FS	0.36575	0.09754
Linear Regression	Yeo-Johnson	CAR Score	0.36708	0.09237
Linear Regression	Yeo-Johnson	Boruta	0.36718	0.09052
Linear Regression	Percentile	No FS	0.24033	0.12088
Linear Regression	Percentile	CAR Score	0.24234	0.11599
Linear Regression	Percentile	Boruta	0.24212	0.11829
Decision Tree	No Transformation	No FS	6.52040	0.00023
Decision Tree	No Transformation	CAR Score	6.52040	0.00023
Decision Tree	No Transformation	Boruta	6.63881	0.00001
Decision Tree	Square Root	No FS	0.70430	0.03795
Decision Tree	Square Root	CAR Score	0.70430	0.03795
Decision Tree	Square Root	Boruta	0.70430	0.03795
Decision Tree	Yeo-Johnson	No FS	0.36171	0.12024

Decision Tree	Yeo-Johnson	CAR Score	0.36171	0.12024
Decision Tree	Yeo-Johnson	Boruta	0.36171	0.12024
Decision Tree	Percentile	No FS	0.23633	0.16161
Decision Tree	Percentile	CAR Score	0.23633	0.16161
Decision Tree	Percentile	Boruta	0.23633	0.16161
Random Forest	No Transformation	No FS	6.27390	0.00111
Random Forest	No Transformation	CAR Score	6.31046	0.00151
Random Forest	No Transformation	Boruta	6.42456	0.00119
Random Forest	Square Root	No FS	0.68568	0.04683
Random Forest	Square Root	CAR Score	0.69401	0.04131
Random Forest	Square Root	Boruta	0.69720	0.03417
Random Forest	Yeo-Johnson	No FS	0.35224	0.16525
Random Forest	Yeo-Johnson	CAR Score	0.35702	0.14259
Random Forest	Yeo-Johnson	Boruta	0.35417	0.14961
Random Forest	Percentile	No FS	0.23219	0.20053
Random Forest	Percentile	CAR Score	0.23525	0.17718
Random Forest	Percentile	Boruta	0.23265	0.19014
Extreme Gradient Boosting	No Transformation	No FS	6.25981	0.00147
Extreme Gradient Boosting	No Transformation	CAR Score	6.28595	0.00163
Extreme Gradient Boosting	No Transformation	Boruta	6.86291	0.00019
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Square Root	No FS	0.69626	0.03812
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Square Root	CAR Score	0.69919	0.03324
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Square Root	Boruta	0.73438	0.02251
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Yeo-Johnson	No FS	0.35103	0.16206
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Yeo-Johnson	CAR Score	0.35770	0.13457
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Yeo-Johnson	Boruta	0.37880	0.05148
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Percentile	No FS	0.22943	0.17927
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Percentile	CAR Score	0.23294	0.15501
Extreme Gradient Boosting	Percentile	Boruta	0.24984	0.05534
K-Nearest Neighbors	No Transformation	No FS	6.69434	0.00008

K-Nearest Neighbors	No Transformation	CAR Score	6.70183	0.00081
K-Nearest Neighbors	No Transformation	Boruta	6.82714	0.00006
K-Nearest Neighbors	Square Root	No FS	0.78117	0.01016
K-Nearest Neighbors	Square Root	CAR Score	0.83839	0.00020
K-Nearest Neighbors	Square Root	Boruta	0.77854	0.00805
K-Nearest Neighbors	Yeo-Johnson	No FS	0.40720	0.07428
K-Nearest Neighbors	Yeo-Johnson	CAR Score	0.46071	0.01680
K-Nearest Neighbors	Yeo-Johnson	Boruta	0.40126	0.08045
K-Nearest Neighbors	Percentile	No FS	0.24795	0.10342
K-Nearest Neighbors	Percentile	CAR Score	0.27582	0.02240
K-Nearest Neighbors	Percentile	Boruta	0.24460	0.10607

- Note: Best model per algorithm based on initial evaluation is in **bold text and highlighted in blue.**